

THE IMPORTANCE OF A REFLECTIVE-ASSESSMENT POSITION IN THE PROFESSIONAL SELF-DEVELOPMENT OF HISTORY TEACHERS

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Abstract. *In this article, the importance of the reflexive-evaluation position in the professional self-development of the teacher is scientifically and pedagogically based. Also, the main functions of the reflexive-evaluation position of the teacher are defined.*

Keywords: *professional self-development, reflexive-evaluation position, pedagogical activity, motive, concept "I".*

In a rapidly changing social environment, self-development is one of the main competencies, because only an actively developing specialist can meet the requirements of the times and the new requirements of the professional environment. In modern conditions, specialists striving for continuous professional improvement and self-development are becoming the main resource for socio-economic changes and the introduction of innovative technologies in various spheres of society. The effectiveness of solving non-standard tasks in constantly changing conditions is directly related to the process and results of personal and professional self-development.

Professional self-development of a teacher is a complex and contradictory process of self-improvement, organization of personal and professional qualities, knowledge and skills, objective control of one's activity and its results. It requires the ability (skills) of self-awareness, learning and self-assessment from the teacher.

This is done primarily on the basis of developing a reflexive-evaluative position. Its formation is carried out on the basis of the theory and practice of pedagogical reflection and requires the teacher to have appropriate knowledge and skills. The presence of a reflexive-evaluative position in the teacher's pedagogical activity allows him to understand and evaluate the pedagogical and social significance of the professional-pedagogical experience and the achieved results in a maximally constructive and balanced, holistic and systematic way, to identify educational problems, strengths and weaknesses, the causes of problems, allows you to determine the ways of optimal self-improvement and self-education.

Currently, the successes achieved as a result of the implementation of reflexive activities of pedagogical teams in educational institutions indicate that reflection is becoming one of the important criteria of education and training.

A.A.Khalikov researched the directions of formation and development of reflexive skills in future teachers as follows: formation of ideas about reflections and reflexive abilities; mastering and developing reflexive skills in pedagogical practice based on self-analysis and diagnosis, making corrections to one's professional activity; creating a special system of forming reflexive skills in students and reorganizing the educational process accordingly [3].

In his research, S.Y.Makhmudov showed the level of readiness of pedagogues for personal and professional development, the change of their motivation for innovative-variational training,

the increase of self-assessment of pedagogues, self-reflection believes that it is related to having methods [2].

In current modern pedagogical research, many scientists positively approach the classification of reflection proposed by S.Y.Stepanov and I.N.Semyonov [5]. He distinguishes the following types of reflection and their areas of scientific research: intellectual, personal, communicative, cooperative reflection.

We try to systematize the main aspects of the teacher's reflexive and evaluative position formation process as a condition for his effective professional self-development.

In this case, general thinking ability is presented as a set of individual skills (elements), in particular:

- the ability to control one's actions, including mental actions;
- monitoring the movements of one's thoughts;
- to be able to see the conflict that is the cause of the movement of thought;
- implementation of a dialectical approach in analyzing the situation;
- taking the position of various "observers";
- change the explanation of the observed or analyzed event depending on the goals and conditions;
- use of theoretical methods of knowledge in order to analyze knowledge, its structure and content;
- to determine the sequence and location of the stages of development and self-development on the basis of reflecting on one's own experience, the foundations of previous activities, problems and achievements, causes and meaning.

Common symptoms of this process:

- the teacher's ability to solve non-standard pedagogical problems;
- creating together, looking for new things;
- the desire and ability to study and evaluate the importance of the results of one's own ideas and activities, to evaluate their effectiveness and optimality.

The above allows us to distinguish the essence of the teacher's reflexive-evaluation position as a psychological-pedagogical mechanism and the main points that reflect the conditions of the teacher's professional self-development:

- assessment, development and implementation of a system of generalized methods of pedagogical activity, including the teacher's ability to act effectively in pedagogical activity, and determination of the value-semantic content of developing oneself and others from it;
- the ability (ability and readiness) to choose appropriate means and methods of developing oneself and others based on the design of effective pedagogical activity in the context of subject-subject interaction;
- directing the teacher to consciously choose opportunities for professional self-development, forming the need for pedagogical creativity.

From these positions, the main functions of the teacher's reflexive-evaluation position can be distinguished:

- self-awareness - orientation to the value-semantic content of individual behavior, to know one's needs, interests, inclinations, etc., to determine the teacher's self, current, previous and future position;

- self-design - intellectual forecast for the future, accurate planning of one's activities in time, that is, life and professional plans;

- self-organization - the ability to direct oneself and one's actions to achieve a specific goal, to implement the process of self-development;

- self-analysis (introspection) - the ability to analyze one's 'I', the results of one's pedagogical activity;

- self-regulation - the teacher's ability to control and correct his own behavior.

Based on the functional characteristics of the teacher's reflexive-evaluation position, its principles can be distinguished: variability, awareness, reflexive (reflective), reliance on experience, individuality, self-organization, activity, interaction effect.

The principle of variability - directs each teacher to develop his own professional-pedagogical activity program and strategy, a unique individual direction of professional self-development, as well as the qualities of the teacher's personality allows you to create a holistic picture of

The principle of consciousness defines the attitude of the teacher to accept and understand the complex goal of professional self-development as personally important, and defines a step-by-step program of actions that shows the expected result.

The reflexive (reflective) principle implies an individual creative approach to the acquisition of knowledge using modern educational technologies, and the reflexive goal of professional activity is not to form a certain abstract system of certain knowledge and methods of action, but to be a person, criteria requires. The initial stage of such activity should begin with the analysis of certain professional and personal difficulties. Identifying these difficulties, analyzing their nature and causes allows to choose the content and forms of professional self-development that matches the needs of each teacher in the school environment.

The principle of relying on experience - allows the formation of a professional personality within a specific activity, implements the idea of using and revising the existing reflective and evaluation experience by the teacher, works as one of the sources of self-learning, as well as, defines the relationship between cognitive processes, logic and results.

The principle of individuality includes the choice of the most appropriate ways and methods of achieving the goal, taking into account the individual characteristics of each teacher in terms of the issues being studied, actions being taken, and the content of the activity.

The principle of self-organization determines the individual meaning of the perception of information by each teacher and the possibility of reflecting his actions in the process of self-education. The content of such self-education becomes the standard methods of activity that reveal the mechanisms of any change and development.

The principle of activity - this principle implies the following: information content is selected according to the main activity of the teacher, his professional and personal problems; real situations are reflected in the teacher's practical activities in ensuring professional self-development; the importance of thinking about one's own experience and activity results increases.

The principle of interaction. Mandatory element of professional self-development is direct interaction between teacher and learner, teacher and school leader, teachers. It refers to communication, professional interaction. Only in mutual communication (cooperation, co-creation) can a professional develop reflexive knowledge and skills as the basis and conditions of self-development.

For each teacher, this process is carried out in a unique way, taking into account individual characteristics and conditions of implementation, depending on general trends.

Factors determining the specificity (character) of the manifestation of professional self-development from the point of view of the reflexive-evaluative position of the teacher include:

- a personal factor that forms motivations, basic reflexive-analytical needs and activity in self-knowledge and creative activity;

- the analytical direction of the teacher as a set of methodological ideas that have become a guide and scientifically based tool for all professional and pedagogical activities;

- continuous analysis and introspection of the results of one's activity through evaluation activities, development of "I-concept".

The reflexive (reflective)-evaluation activity in the implementation of the teacher's self-professional development includes the following components:

- motivational - refers to the direction of the teacher's conscious attitude to professional self-development as a condition for effective activity;

- meaningful - combines the sum of knowledge, skills and competencies of the teacher's reflexive and evaluation activities;

- operational - reflects the teacher's reflective-evaluative activity; describes the teacher's knowledge and analysis of the specific characteristics of his professional activity, achievements, problems and difficulties;

- design - includes the teacher's constructive activity, during which the "I-concept" is created, personal resources are created.

In general, the following procedural didactic and methodical scheme of the teacher's self-professional development can be imagined in the context of his pedagogical reflexive and evaluation position:

1. A teacher's understanding of the main signs, norms and rules of his profession as a criterion for understanding his qualities and characteristics. This allows teachers to establish relationships with others, to evaluate themselves appropriately.

2. Realizing these qualities in others. Comparing oneself to a certain professional image, both abstractly and as a specific person.

3. Taking into account the evaluation (of oneself as a professional) given by students, parents, colleagues, management and other subjects of pedagogical interaction.

4. Prospects for self-professional development based on the teacher's unique aspects (weak and strong), his pedagogical activity, results (successes and failures), formed reflexive skills.

5. Formation of reflective experience as a basis for comprehensive (positive) self-evaluation, determination of self-development strategy, optimal (effective) professional activity and self-development design.

It seems that all the above features of the reflexive-evaluation position, its functions, principles and components are closely related to each other in order to realize the process of self-development, and the teacher's professional interaction "secret" determines the effectiveness of the teacher's professional self-development by creating the appropriate content of the self-education process and conditions. This is the most effective option for the teacher's professional self-development (self-knowledge, self-organization, self-discipline and self-awareness) through conscious and creates conditions for providing reflexive (reflective)-evaluation preparation for reasonable selection.

The conclusion is that the need for continuous self-development based on the content and functions of professional-pedagogical activity determines the requirements for the level of professional skills of the teacher and his personal qualities. It is important for the teacher to be able to identify and implement the priorities of his activity, as well as to solve professional problems in mobile and creative ways.

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